

Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15

The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9212>

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Abstract

*Recently, author [69] worked with **cornered** magic squares of order 6. Later this work is extended up to order 24 [69, 70, 71]. This work is for odd order magic squares. It for the orders 3 to 15. In this work we have covered three types of magic squares. One **centered** magic squares. These are traditionally previous known magic squares. The second one is **double digits bordered** magic squares. The third one is **cornered** magic squares. Some embedded examples are given where one type is embedded in another type. Further studies of orders 17, 19, 21, 23 and 25 refer author's work [66, 67, 68].*

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1 Introduction

Recently, author worked with **cornered magic squares** based on two-by-two digits:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13 [69, 70].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24 [71].

Also, the author worked on **even order double digits bordered** magic squares. This works starts from order 8 and goes up to order 40:

The work for order of type $4k, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, i.e., for orders 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36 and 40:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24 [59].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32 [60].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40[63].

The work is for the order of type $4k + 2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, i.e., for the orders 10, 14, 18, 22, 26, 30, 34 and 38:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22 [61].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30 [62].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Order 34 and 38 [64].

2 Odd Orders Magic Squares

In this work, we shall construct odd order magic squares starting from order 3. It is of different types of **odd** order magic squares. It includes:

1. Centered magic squares.
2. Double digits bordered magic squares.
3. Bordered magic squares with borders of orders 3, 5, etc.
4. Cornered magic squares.

To construct **double digits** and **cornered** magic squares using software, the reader can follow H. Whites site [1]. Moreover, the **cornered** magic squares can be written in any of the four directions by using H. Whites [1] rotate program. Few examples can be seen at author's work [70, 71].

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Below is a well-known magic square of order 3.

			15
4	9	2	15
3	5	7	15
8	1	6	15
15	15	15	15

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three different types of magic squares of order 5. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

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	pan	65	65	65	65	65
65	1	7	13	19	25	65
65	18	24	5	6	12	65
65	10	11	17	23	4	65
65	22	3	9	15	16	65
	14	20	21	2	8	65
1	65	65	65	65	65	65
	2					65
	22	25	5	7	6	65
	2	12	17	10	24	65
	3	11	13	15	23	65
	18	16	9	14	8	65
	20	1	21	19	4	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65
	3					65
	16	11	12	23	3	65
	9	13	17	25	1	65
	14	15	10	7	19	65
	5	6	22	8	24	65
	21	20	4	2	18	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

The first magic square is **pandiagonal** magic square. The second one is **bordered** magic square. The third one is **cornered** magic square. To see all the four directions of **cornered** magic square refer author's work [66]

2.3 Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are six different types of magic squares of order 7. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

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	pan	175	175	175	175	175	175
175	1	9	17	25	33	41	49
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27
	18	26	34	42	43	2	10
1	175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	2 mgc	200	190	180	170	160	150
	42	38	40	5	4	2	44
	1	34	37	17	19	18	49
	3	14	24	29	22	36	47
	43	15	23	25	27	35	7
	41	30	28	21	26	20	9
	39	32	13	33	31	16	11
	6	12	10	45	46	48	8
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	3 mgc	200	190	180	170	160	150
	4	30	44	32	15	13	37
	46	20	6	18	35	9	41
	34	16	26	21	28	17	33
	42	8	27	25	23	47	3
	43	7	22	29	24	39	11
	1	49	48	12	19	36	10
	5	45	2	38	31	14	40
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/							https://numbers-magic.com/							@IJTANEJA													
4	mgc	200	190	180	170	160	150	175	5	mgc	200	190	180	170	160	150	175	6	mgc	200	190	180	170	160	150	175			
		26	21	28	30	20	8	42	175			13	19	25	31	37	12	38	175			34	37	19	17	18	12	38	175
		27	25	23	33	17	12	38	175			30	36	17	18	24	8	42	175			14	24	29	22	36	8	42	175
		22	29	24	14	36	48	2	175			22	23	29	35	16	48	2	175			30	23	25	27	20	48	2	175
		34	32	31	13	15	45	5	175			34	15	21	27	28	45	5	175			15	28	21	26	35	45	5	175
		16	18	19	35	37	10	40	175			26	32	33	14	20	10	40	175			32	13	31	33	16	10	40	175
		46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175			46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175			47	49	7	46	6	11	9	175
		4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175			4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175			3	1	43	4	44	41	39	175
		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Magic squares 1 and 2 are **centered** magic squares. The first magic square is **pandiagonal**. Magic square 3 is **double digits bordered** magic square. Magic squares 4, 5 and 6 are **cornered** magic squares. It includes as traditional magic squares of orders 3 and 5.

2.4 Magic Squares of Order 9

Below are 11 different types of magic squares of order 9. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

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	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	2													
369		22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369			8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
369		35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369			1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	369
369		66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369			3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	369
369		40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369			5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	369
369		80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369			73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	369
369		3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369			71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	369
369		58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369			69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	369
369		17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369			67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	369
		48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369			72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
1		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369			369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

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3										4									
69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369	69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369
13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369	13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369
73	9	38	34	51	32	50	6	76	369	73	9	50	53	35	33	34	6	76	369
68	14	44	48	31	39	43	79	3	369	68	14	30	40	45	38	52	79	3	369
11	71	46	36	41	52	30	7	75	369	11	71	46	39	41	43	36	7	75	369
78	4	42	40	53	33	37	59	23	369	78	4	31	44	37	42	51	59	23	369
19	63	35	47	29	49	45	22	60	369	19	63	48	29	47	49	32	22	60	369
20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369	20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369
18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369	18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
5																			
69	16	80	12	72	17	21	56	26	369										
13	66	2	70	10	65	61	58	24	369										
73	9	44	39	40	51	31	6	76	369										
68	14	37	41	45	53	29	79	3	369										
11	71	42	43	38	35	47	7	75	369										
78	4	33	34	50	36	52	59	23	369										
19	63	49	48	32	30	46	22	60	369										
20	62	55	25	77	8	67	1	54	369										
18	64	27	57	5	74	15	81	28	369										
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369										

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6										369									
38	43	42	50	32	27	55	15	67	369	29	35	41	47	53	27	55	8	74	369
45	41	37	46	36	62	20	8	74	369	46	52	33	34	40	62	20	15	67	369
40	39	44	49	33	26	56	80	2	369	38	39	45	51	32	26	56	80	2	369
34	35	52	31	53	65	17	10	72	369	50	31	37	43	44	65	17	10	72	369
48	47	30	29	51	23	59	14	68	369	42	48	49	30	36	23	59	14	68	369
60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369	60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369
22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369	22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369
78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369	78	76	16	13	79	75	12	11	9	369
4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369	4	6	66	69	3	7	70	73	71	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

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8										9										369
50	53	35	33	34	27	55	8	74	369	20	46	60	48	31	29	53	10	72	369	
30	40	45	38	52	62	20	15	67	369	62	36	22	34	51	25	57	15	67	369	
46	39	41	43	36	26	56	80	2	369	50	32	42	37	44	33	49	80	2	369	
31	44	37	42	51	65	17	10	72	369	58	24	43	41	39	63	19	8	74	369	
48	29	47	49	32	23	59	14	68	369	59	23	38	45	40	55	27	14	68	369	
60	54	57	18	58	21	19	77	5	369	17	65	64	28	35	52	26	77	5	369	
22	28	25	64	24	63	61	81	1	369	21	61	18	54	47	30	56	81	1	369	
76	78	16	13	79	75	12	11	9	369	76	78	16	13	79	75	12	11	9	369	
6	4	66	69	3	7	70	73	71	369	6	4	66	69	3	7	70	73	71	369	
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	

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10										11									
17	25	33	41	49	57	65	8	74	369	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	15	67	369
56	64	23	24	32	40	48	10	72	369	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	8	74	369
39	47	55	63	22	30	31	80	2	369	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	80	2	369
29	37	38	46	54	62	21	15	67	369	59	46	39	41	43	36	23	10	72	369
61	20	28	36	44	45	53	14	68	369	57	31	44	37	42	51	25	14	68	369
51	52	60	19	27	35	43	77	5	369	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	77	5	369
34	42	50	58	59	18	26	81	1	369	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	81	1	369
78	75	16	13	79	76	12	11	9	369	79	75	16	13	78	76	12	11	9	369
4	7	66	69	3	6	70	73	71	369	3	7	66	69	4	6	70	73	71	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Magic squares 1 and 2 are **centered** magic squares. Magic square 3 is **double digits bordered** magic square. Magic squares 4, 5 and 6 are **cornered** magic squares. It includes as traditional magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7.

Still there is one more magic squares, i.e., **bimagic square**. It can be seen in author’s work [8]

2.5 Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are 19 different types of magic squares of order 11. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/													https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												
671	pan	671	2	mgc	622	651	662	698	669	675	644	680	691	718	671										
671	1	21	30	39	48	57	77	86	95	104	113	671	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
671	101	121	9	18	27	36	45	65	74	83	92	671	121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1	671	
671	80	89	109	118	6	15	24	44	53	62	71	671	119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3	671	
671	59	68	88	97	106	115	3	12	32	41	50	671	117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5	671	
671	38	47	56	76	85	94	103	112	11	20	29	671	115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7	671	
671	17	26	35	55	64	73	82	91	100	120	8	671	11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111	671	
671	117	5	14	23	43	52	61	70	79	99	108	671	13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109	671	
671	96	105	114	2	22	31	40	49	58	67	87	671	15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107	671	
671	75	84	93	102	111	10	19	28	37	46	66	671	17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105	671	
671	54	63	72	81	90	110	119	7	16	25	34	671	19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103	671	
	33	42	51	60	69	78	98	107	116	4	13	671	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
1	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

3	mgc	612	702	646	604	700	638	734	700	644	730	671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671
	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671
	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671
	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671
	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671
	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671
	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671
	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671
	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

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4	mgc	842	577	493	682	702	772	590	824	607	621	671	5	mgc	826	593	511	711	627	755	652	798	610	627	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671	
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671	
		100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28			100	22	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	94	28	671	
		8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91			8	114	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	31	91	671	
		107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98			107	15	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	24	98	671	
		96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11			96	26	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	111	11	671	
		35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97			35	87	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	25	97	671	
		104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103			104	18	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	19	103	671	
		6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2			6	116	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	120	2	671	
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

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6	mgc	810	603	542	683	698	743	641	821	580	589	671	7	mgc	796	641	448	707	673	783	639	838	589	596	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671	
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671	
		100	22	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	94	28			100	22	62	57	64	66	56	44	78	94	28	671	
		8	114	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	31	91			8	114	63	61	59	69	53	48	74	31	91	671	
		107	15	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	24	98			107	15	58	65	60	50	72	84	38	24	98	671	
		96	26	79	66	59	61	63	56	43	111	11			96	26	70	68	67	49	51	81	41	111	11	671	
		35	87	77	51	64	57	62	71	45	25	97			35	87	52	54	55	71	73	46	76	25	97	671	
		104	18	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	19	103			104	18	82	85	43	83	42	47	45	19	103	671	
		6	116	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	120	2			6	116	40	37	79	39	80	77	75	120	2	671	
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

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8	mgc	792	624	448	707	660	784	647	827	589	632	671	9	mgc	818	619	449	707	681	786	637	806	589	618	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671
		100	22	49	55	61	67	73	48	74	94	28	671			100	22	70	73	55	53	54	48	74	94	28	671
		8	114	66	72	53	54	60	44	78	31	91	671			8	114	50	60	65	58	72	44	78	31	91	671
		107	15	58	59	65	71	52	84	38	24	98	671			107	15	66	59	61	63	56	84	38	24	98	671
		96	26	70	51	57	63	64	81	41	111	11	671			96	26	51	64	57	62	71	81	41	111	11	671
		35	87	62	68	69	50	56	46	76	25	97	671			35	87	68	49	67	69	52	46	76	25	97	671
		104	18	82	85	43	83	42	47	45	19	103	671			104	18	83	85	43	82	42	47	45	19	103	671
		6	116	40	37	79	39	80	77	75	120	2	671			6	116	39	37	79	40	80	77	75	120	2	671
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA															
10	mgc	745	623	705	544	779	772	574	607	707	654	671	11	mgc	736	616	713	567	779	766	566	599	714	654	671		
		58	63	62	54	68	48	74	87	35	13	109	671			49	55	61	67	73	48	74	87	35	13	109	671
		65	61	57	55	67	44	78	24	98	104	18	671			66	72	53	54	60	44	78	24	98	104	18	671
		60	59	64	72	50	84	38	25	97	8	114	671			58	59	65	71	52	84	38	25	97	8	114	671
		56	52	53	73	71	81	41	89	33	3	119	671			70	51	57	63	64	81	41	89	33	3	119	671
		66	70	69	51	49	46	76	92	30	106	16	671			62	68	69	50	56	46	76	92	30	106	16	671
		83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671			83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671
		39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671			39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671
		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671			21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671			101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671			120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671			2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												
12 mgc	75	7	618	701	548	779	751	569	623	710	654	671	13 mgc	703	587	718	538	800	760	567	633	680	724	671
70	73	53	55	54	48	74	87	35	13	109	671	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	87	35	13	109	671	
50	60	65	58	72	44	78	24	98	104	18	671	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	25	97	104	18	671	
66	59	61	63	56	84	38	25	97	8	114	671	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	24	98	8	114	671	
51	64	57	62	71	81	41	89	33	3	119	671	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	89	33	3	119	671	
68	49	69	67	52	46	76	92	30	106	16	671	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	92	30	106	16	671	
83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	29	93	5	117	671	
39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	23	99	105	17	671	
21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671	21	91	96	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671	
101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671	101	31	26	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671	
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											
14 mgc	779	570	755	556	732	722	567	617	652	760	671	15 mgc	670	593	803	438	838	803	559	601	671	734	671
78	74	76	41	40	38	80	87	35	13	109	671	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	5	117	671
37	70	73	53	55	54	85	25	97	104	18	671	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	104	18	671
77	50	60	65	58	72	45	29	93	8	114	671	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	8	114	671
79	66	59	61	63	56	43	89	33	3	119	671	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	3	119	671
39	51	64	57	62	71	83	92	30	106	16	671	93	79	66	59	61	63	56	43	29	106	16	671
75	68	49	69	67	52	47	24	98	5	117	671	91	77	51	64	57	62	71	45	31	13	109	671
42	48	46	81	82	84	44	23	99	105	17	671	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	105	17	671
21	91	96	22	88	90	27	86	28	108	14	671	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	108	14	671
101	31	26	100	34	32	95	94	36	107	15	671	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	107	15	671
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											
16 mgc	566	806	752	569	644	794	608	586	671	714	671	17 mgc	607	720	859	471	713	774	511	667	671	717	671
42	91	50	47	84	52	58	26	99	13	109	671	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	3	119	671
55	41	87	48	43	92	98	63	22	108	14	671	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671
86	51	46	88	56	39	27	94	62	8	114	671	93	29	64	59	60	71	51	42	80	8	114	671
60	28	95	65	21	97	40	89	54	5	117	671	88	34	57	61	65	73	49	79	43	5	117	671
100	59	24	93	61	29	53	45	85	106	16	671	31	91	62	63	58	55	67	27	95	106	16	671
23	96	64	25	101	57	90	49	44	3	119	671	98	24	53	54	70	56	72	99	23	13	109	671
78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	105	17	671	39	83	69	68	52	50	66	26	96	105	17	671
37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	104	18	671	40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671
68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	107	15	671	38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671
118	11	19	116	121	115	9	120	12	10	20	671	115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	10	20	671
4	111	103	6	1	7	113	2	110	102	112	671	7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											
18 mgc	591	699	895	442	720	776	533	636	671	747	671	19 mgc	625	706	859	461	729	781	509	643	671	726	671
89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	13	109	671	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	13	109	671
33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671
93	29	58	54	71	52	70	26	96	8	114	671	93	29	70	73	55	53	54	42	80	8	114	671
88	34	64	68	51	59	63	99	23	5	117	671	88	34	50	60	65	58	72	79	43	5	117	671
31	91	66	56	61	72	50	27	95	106	16	671	31	91	66	59	61	63	56	27	95	106	16	671
98	24	62	60	73	53	57	79	43	3	119	671	98	24	51	64	57	62	71	99	23	3	119	671
39	83	55	67	49	69	65	42	80	105	17	671	39	83	68	49	67	69	52	26	96	105	17	671
40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671	40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671
38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671	38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671
118	11	19	116	121	115	9	120	12	10	20	671	115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	10	20	671
4	111	103	6	1	7	113	2	110	102	112	671	7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

2.6 Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are 19 different types of magic squares of order 11. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/													https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												
pan	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	2	mgc	622	651	662	698	669	675	644	680	691	718	671
671	1	21	30	39	48	57	77	86	95	104	113	671	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
671	101	121	9	18	27	36	45	65	74	83	92	671	121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1	671	
671	80	89	109	118	6	15	24	44	53	62	71	671	119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3	671	
671	59	68	88	97	106	115	3	12	32	41	50	671	117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5	671	
671	38	47	56	76	85	94	103	112	11	20	29	671	115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7	671	
671	17	26	35	55	64	73	82	91	100	120	8	671	11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111	671	
671	117	5	14	23	43	52	61	70	79	99	108	671	13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109	671	
671	96	105	114	2	22	31	40	49	58	67	87	671	15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107	671	
671	75	84	93	102	111	10	19	28	37	46	66	671	17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105	671	
671	54	63	72	81	90	110	119	7	16	25	34	671	19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103	671	
1	33	42	51	60	69	78	98	107	116	4	13	671	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

3	mgc	612	702	646	604	700	638	734	700	644	730	671
12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671	
119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671	
117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671	
115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671	
11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671	
13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671	
15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671	
17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671	
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671	
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA															
4	mgc	842	577	493	682	702	772	590	824	607	621	671	5	mgc	826	593	511	711	627	755	652	798	610	627	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671	
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671	
		100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28			100	22	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	94	28	671	
		8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91			8	114	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	31	91	671	
		107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98			107	15	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	24	98	671	
		96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11			96	26	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	111	11	671	
		35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97			35	87	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	25	97	671	
		104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103			104	18	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	19	103	671	
		6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2			6	116	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	120	2	671	
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA															
6	mgc	810	603	542	683	698	743	641	821	580	589	671	7	mgc	796	641	448	707	673	783	639	838	589	596	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671	
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671	
		100	22	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	94	28			100	22	62	57	64	66	56	44	78	94	28	671	
		8	114	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	31	91			8	114	63	61	59	69	53	48	74	31	91	671	
		107	15	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	24	98			107	15	58	65	60	50	72	84	38	24	98	671	
		96	26	79	66	59	61	63	56	43	111	11			96	26	70	68	67	49	51	81	41	111	11	671	
		35	87	77	51	64	57	62	71	45	25	97			35	87	52	54	55	71	73	46	76	25	97	671	
		104	18	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	19	103			104	18	82	85	43	83	42	47	45	19	103	671	
		6	116	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	120	2			6	116	40	37	79	39	80	77	75	120	2	671	
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/													https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														
8	mgc	792	624	448	707	660	784	647	827	589	632	671	9	mgc	818	619	449	707	681	786	637	806	589	618	671		
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671			112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671			10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671
		100	22	49	55	61	67	73	48	74	94	28	671			100	22	70	73	55	53	54	48	74	94	28	671
		8	114	66	72	53	54	60	44	78	31	91	671			8	114	50	60	65	58	72	44	78	31	91	671
		107	15	58	59	65	71	52	84	38	24	98	671			107	15	66	59	61	63	56	84	38	24	98	671
		96	26	70	51	57	63	64	81	41	111	11	671			96	26	51	64	57	62	71	81	41	111	11	671
		35	87	62	68	69	50	56	46	76	25	97	671			35	87	68	49	67	69	52	46	76	25	97	671
		104	18	82	85	43	83	42	47	45	19	103	671			104	18	83	85	43	82	42	47	45	19	103	671
		6	116	40	37	79	39	80	77	75	120	2	671			6	116	39	37	79	40	80	77	75	120	2	671
		4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671			4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
		89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671			89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/													https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														
10	mgc	745	623	705	544	779	772	574	607	707	654	671	11	mgc	736	616	713	567	779	766	566	599	714	654	671		
		58	63	62	54	68	48	74	87	35	13	109	671			49	55	61	67	73	48	74	87	35	13	109	671
		65	61	57	55	67	44	78	24	98	104	18	671			66	72	53	54	60	44	78	24	98	104	18	671
		60	59	64	72	50	84	38	25	97	8	114	671			58	59	65	71	52	84	38	25	97	8	114	671
		56	52	53	73	71	81	41	89	33	3	119	671			70	51	57	63	64	81	41	89	33	3	119	671
		66	70	69	51	49	46	76	92	30	106	16	671			62	68	69	50	56	46	76	92	30	106	16	671
		83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671			83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671
		39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671			39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671
		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671			21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671			101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671			120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671			2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671			671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.com/												https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												
12 mgc	75	7	618	701	548	779	751	569	623	710	654	671	13 mgc	703	587	718	538	800	760	567	633	680	724	671
70	73	53	55	54	48	74	87	35	13	109	671	37	45	53	61	69	77	85	87	35	13	109	671	
50	60	65	58	72	44	78	24	98	104	18	671	76	84	43	44	52	60	68	25	97	104	18	671	
66	59	61	63	56	84	38	25	97	8	114	671	59	67	75	83	42	50	51	24	98	8	114	671	
51	64	57	62	71	81	41	89	33	3	119	671	49	57	58	66	74	82	41	89	33	3	119	671	
68	49	69	67	52	46	76	92	30	106	16	671	81	40	48	56	64	65	73	92	30	106	16	671	
83	85	43	82	42	47	45	29	93	5	117	671	71	72	80	39	47	55	63	29	93	5	117	671	
39	37	79	40	80	77	75	23	99	105	17	671	54	62	70	78	79	38	46	23	99	105	17	671	
21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671	21	91	96	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671	
101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671	101	31	26	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671	
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

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14 mgc	779	570	755	556	732	722	567	617	652	760	671	15 mgc	670	593	803	438	838	803	559	601	671	734	671
78	74	76	41	40	38	80	87	35	13	109	671	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	5	117	671
37	70	73	53	55	54	85	25	97	104	18	671	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	104	18	671
77	50	60	65	58	72	45	29	93	8	114	671	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	8	114	671
79	66	59	61	63	56	43	89	33	3	119	671	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	3	119	671
39	51	64	57	62	71	83	92	30	106	16	671	93	79	66	59	61	63	56	43	29	106	16	671
75	68	49	69	67	52	47	24	98	5	117	671	91	77	51	64	57	62	71	45	31	13	109	671
42	48	46	81	82	84	44	23	99	105	17	671	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	105	17	671
21	91	96	22	88	90	27	86	28	108	14	671	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	108	14	671
101	31	26	100	34	32	95	94	36	107	15	671	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	107	15	671
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

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16 mgc	566	806	752	569	644	794	608	586	671	714	671	17 mgc	607	720	859	471	713	774	511	667	671	717	671
42	91	50	47	84	52	58	26	99	13	109	671	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	3	119	671
55	41	87	48	43	92	98	63	22	108	14	671	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671
86	51	46	88	56	39	27	94	62	8	114	671	93	29	64	59	60	71	51	42	80	8	114	671
60	28	95	65	21	97	40	89	54	5	117	671	88	34	57	61	65	73	49	79	43	5	117	671
100	59	24	93	61	29	53	45	85	106	16	671	31	91	62	63	58	55	67	27	95	106	16	671
23	96	64	25	101	57	90	49	44	3	119	671	98	24	53	54	70	56	72	99	23	13	109	671
78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	105	17	671	39	83	69	68	52	50	66	26	96	105	17	671
37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	104	18	671	40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671
68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	107	15	671	38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671
118	11	19	116	121	115	9	120	12	10	20	671	115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	10	20	671
4	111	103	6	1	7	113	2	110	102	112	671	7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

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18 mgc	591	699	895	442	720	776	533	636	671	747	671	19 mgc	625	706	859	461	729	781	509	643	671	726	671
89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	13	109	671	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	76	46	13	109	671
33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	78	44	108	14	671
93	29	58	54	71	52	70	26	96	8	114	671	93	29	70	73	55	53	54	42	80	8	114	671
88	34	64	68	51	59	63	99	23	5	117	671	88	34	50	60	65	58	72	79	43	5	117	671
31	91	66	56	61	72	50	27	95	106	16	671	31	91	66	59	61	63	56	27	95	106	16	671
98	24	62	60	73	53	57	79	43	3	119	671	98	24	51	64	57	62	71	99	23	3	119	671
39	83	55	67	49	69	65	42	80	105	17	671	39	83	68	49	67	69	52	26	96	105	17	671
40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671	40	82	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	104	18	671
38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671	38	84	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	107	15	671
118	11	19	116	121	115	9	120	12	10	20	671	115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	10	20	671
4	111	103	6	1	7	113	2	110	102	112	671	7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	102	112	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

Magic squares 1, 2 and 3 are **centered** magic squares. The first one is **pandiagonal**. Magic squares 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 are **double digits bordered** magic squares. Magic squares 10 to 19 are **cornered** magic squares. It includes as traditional as well as double digits magic squares of order 5 and 7.

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3													1105		4													1105	
156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12	156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12				
2	25	45	54	63	72	81	101	110	119	128	137	168	2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168				
4	125	145	33	42	51	60	69	89	98	107	116	166	4	145	66	115	74	71	108	76	64	113	78	25	166				
6	104	113	133	142	30	39	48	68	77	86	95	164	6	143	79	65	111	72	67	116	77	69	109	27	164				
8	83	92	112	121	130	139	27	36	56	65	74	162	8	141	110	75	70	112	80	63	114	73	68	29	162				
10	62	71	80	100	109	118	127	136	35	44	53	160	10	139	84	52	119	89	45	121	82	50	123	31	160				
11	41	50	59	79	88	97	106	115	124	144	32	159	11	35	124	83	48	117	85	53	122	87	46	135	159				
154	141	29	38	47	67	76	85	94	103	123	132	16	154	37	47	120	88	49	125	81	51	118	86	133	16				
152	120	129	138	26	46	55	64	73	82	91	111	18	152	39	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	131	18				
150	99	108	117	126	135	34	43	52	61	70	90	20	150	41	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	129	20				
148	78	87	96	105	114	134	143	31	40	49	58	22	148	43	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	127	22				
146	57	66	75	84	93	102	122	131	140	28	37	24	146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24				
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14	158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14				
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105					

Inder J. Taneja													https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/													@IJTANEJA	
5													1105		6													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151				
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34				
44	126	115	119	69	47	54	121	70	108	62	140	30	44	126	115	119	69	47	54	121	70	108	62	140	30				
153	17	55	51	101	123	116	49	100	104	66	127	43	153	17	55	51	101	123	116	49	100	104	66	127	43				
166	4	45	125	76	92	87	84	86	53	117	139	31	166	4	45	125	94	97	77	79	78	53	117	139	31				
146	24	57	113	94	78	83	97	73	46	124	29	141	146	24	57	113	74	84	89	82	96	46	124	29	141				
13	157	112	58	88	82	85	74	96	99	71	33	137	13	157	112	58	90	83	85	87	80	99	71	33	137				
2	168	109	61	90	80	81	95	79	65	105	5	165	2	168	109	61	75	88	81	86	95	65	105	5	165				
25	145	56	114	77	93	89	75	91	120	50	18	152	25	145	56	114	92	73	93	91	76	120	50	18	152				
16	154	106	64	98	63	67	59	68	122	118	142	28	16	154	106	64	98	63	67	59	68	122	118	142	28				
169	1	110	60	72	107	103	111	102	48	52	147	23	169	1	110	60	72	107	103	111	102	48	52	147	23				
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32				
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138				
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105					

Inder J. Taneja													https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/													@IJTANEJA	
7													1105		8													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105		
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105		
44	126	66	115	74	71	108	76	82	50	123	140	30	1105	44	126	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	140	30	1105		
153	17	79	65	111	72	67	116	122	87	46	127	43	1105	153	17	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	127	43	1105		
166	4	110	75	70	112	80	63	51	118	86	139	31	1105	166	4	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	139	31	1105		
146	24	84	52	119	89	45	121	64	113	78	29	141	1105	146	24	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	29	141	1105		
13	157	124	83	48	117	85	53	77	69	109	33	137	1105	13	157	117	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	53	33	137	1105		
2	168	47	120	88	49	125	81	114	73	68	5	165	1105	2	168	115	101	75	88	81	86	95	69	55	5	165	1105		
25	145	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	18	152	1105	25	145	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	18	152	1105		
16	154	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	142	28	1105	16	154	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	142	28	1105		
169	1	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	147	23	1105	169	1	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	147	23	1105		
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105		
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105		
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105			

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9													1105		10													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105		
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105		
44	126	82	87	86	78	92	67	103	111	59	140	30	1105	44	126	73	79	85	91	97	67	103	116	54	140	30	1105		
153	17	89	85	81	79	91	102	68	49	121	127	43	1105	153	17	90	96	77	78	84	102	68	48	122	127	43	1105		
166	4	84	83	88	96	74	99	71	48	122	139	31	1105	166	4	82	83	89	95	76	99	71	49	121	139	31	1105		
146	24	80	76	77	97	95	62	108	113	57	29	141	1105	146	24	94	75	81	87	88	62	108	113	57	29	141	1105		
13	157	90	94	93	75	73	63	107	116	54	33	137	1105	13	157	86	92	93	74	80	63	107	111	59	33	137	1105		
2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105	2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105		
25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105	25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105		
16	154	45	120	115	51	112	114	46	110	52	142	28	1105	16	154	46	120	115	51	112	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105		
169	1	125	50	55	119	58	56	124	118	60	147	23	1105	169	1	124	50	55	119	58	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105		
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105		
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105		
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Inder J. Taneja													https://inderjtaneja.com/	
11													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
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153	17	74	84	89	82	96	102	68	49	121	127	43	1105	
166	4	90	83	85	87	80	99	71	48	122	139	31	1105	
146	24	75	88	81	86	95	62	108	111	59	29	141	1105	
13	157	92	73	93	91	76	63	107	116	54	33	137	1105	
2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105	
25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105	
16	154	46	120	115	51	112	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	124	50	55	119	58	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

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12													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	61	69	77	85	93	101	109	116	54	140	30	1105	
153	17	100	108	67	68	76	84	92	49	121	127	43	1105	
166	4	83	91	99	107	66	74	75	48	122	139	31	1105	
146	24	73	81	82	90	98	106	65	113	57	29	141	1105	
13	157	105	64	72	80	88	89	97	111	59	33	137	1105	
2	168	95	96	104	63	71	79	87	53	117	5	165	1105	
25	145	78	86	94	102	103	62	70	47	123	18	152	1105	
16	154	46	112	120	51	115	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	124	58	50	119	55	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

13													1105	
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	102	98	65	100	64	62	104	116	54	140	30	1105	
153	17	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	47	123	127	43	1105	
166	4	101	74	84	89	82	96	69	53	117	139	31	1105	
146	24	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	113	57	29	141	1105	
13	157	63	75	88	81	86	95	107	111	59	33	137	1105	
2	168	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	48	122	5	165	1105	
25	145	66	72	105	70	106	108	68	49	121	18	152	1105	
16	154	51	112	120	46	115	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	119	58	50	124	55	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

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14												1105												15												1105											
82	87	86	91	79	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	73	79	85	91	97	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105																				
89	85	81	92	78	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105	90	96	77	78	84	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105																				
84	83	88	74	96	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	82	83	89	95	76	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105																				
80	76	77	95	97	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105	94	75	81	87	88	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105																				
90	94	93	73	75	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105	86	92	93	74	80	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105																				
100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105																				
70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105																				
122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105	122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105																				
48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105																				
136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105																				
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16												1105												17												1105											
94	97	77	79	78	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	61	69	77	85	93	101	109	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105																				
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18													1105		19													1105	
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61	94	97	77	79	78	109	121	49	144	26	1	169	1105	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	134	36	1	169	1105		
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63	75	88	81	86	95	107	60	110	39	131	5	165	1105	117	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	53	39	131	5	165	1105		
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124	83	48	117	85	53	77	69	109	39	131	5	165	1105	139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	5	165	1105		
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22												1105		23												1105	
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145	71	108	76	84	52	119	64	113	78	25	147	23	1105	34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105
43	72	67	116	124	83	48	77	69	109	127	8	162	1105	124	46	109	103	66	79	68	74	96	118	52	1	169	1105
141	112	80	63	47	120	88	114	73	68	29	1	169	1105	32	138	61	67	104	91	102	64	106	144	26	6	164	1105
139	102	97	56	89	45	121	82	50	123	31	5	165	1105	131	39	73	97	86	87	82	100	70	48	122	5	165	1105
35	61	101	93	117	85	53	122	87	46	135	6	164	1105	120	50	62	108	81	85	89	94	76	135	35	147	23	1105
37	92	57	106	49	125	81	51	118	86	133	152	18	1105	59	111	90	80	88	83	84	93	77	49	121	152	18	1105
39	66	115	74	107	90	58	100	95	60	131	157	13	1105	128	42	95	75	107	99	69	72	78	43	127	157	13	1105
143	79	65	111	54	103	98	59	105	91	27	155	15	1105	30	140	105	65	63	71	101	98	92	55	115	159	11	1105
41	110	75	70	94	62	99	96	55	104	129	4	166	1105	28	142	119	123	27	36	31	133	56	110	130	4	166	1105
136	128	126	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	149	21	1105	113	57	51	47	143	134	139	37	114	60	40	149	21	1105
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34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	5	165	1105	34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	5	165	1105
124	46	61	69	77	85	93	101	109	118	52	8	162	1105	124	46	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	118	52	8	162	1105
32	138	100	108	67	68	76	84	92	135	35	6	164	1105	32	138	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	135	35	6	164	1105
131	39	83	91	99	107	66	74	75	48	122	1	169	1105	131	39	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	48	122	1	169	1105
120	50	73	81	82	90	98	106	65	144	26	147	23	1105	120	50	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	144	26	147	23	1105
59	111	105	64	72	80	88	89	97	49	121	152	18	1105	59	111	101	75	88	81	86	95	69	49	121	152	18	1105
128	42	95	96	104	63	71	79	87	43	127	157	13	1105	128	42	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	43	127	157	13	1105
30	140	78	86	94	102	103	62	70	55	115	155	15	1105	30	140	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	55	115	159	11	1105
28	142	119	123	27	36	31	133	56	110	130	4	166	1105	28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105
113	57	51	47	143	134	139	37	114	60	40	149	21	1105	113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105
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26												1105	27												1105		
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34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105	34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105
124	46	86	81	88	90	80	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105	124	46	73	79	85	91	97	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105
32	138	87	85	83	93	77	72	98	135	35	6	164	1105	32	138	90	96	77	78	84	72	98	144	26	6	164	1105
131	39	82	89	84	74	96	108	62	48	122	1	169	1105	131	39	82	83	89	95	76	108	62	48	122	1	169	1105
120	50	94	92	91	73	75	105	65	144	26	147	23	1105	120	50	94	75	81	87	88	105	65	135	35	155	15	1105
59	111	76	78	79	95	97	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105	59	111	86	92	93	74	80	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105
128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105	128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105
30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105	30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105
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28												1105	29												1105		
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	147	23	1105	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	157	13	1105
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	6	164	1105	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	1	169	1105
124	46	94	97	79	77	78	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105	143	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	27	8	162	1105
32	138	74	84	89	82	96	72	98	144	26	8	162	1105	141	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	29	6	164	1105
131	39	90	83	85	87	80	105	65	48	122	1	169	1105	139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	5	165	1105
120	50	75	88	81	86	95	108	62	135	35	155	15	1105	35	117	103	75	83	85	87	95	67	53	135	147	23	1105
59	111	92	73	91	93	76	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105	37	115	101	90	88	81	86	80	69	55	133	152	18	1105
128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105	39	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	131	159	11	1105
30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105	41	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	129	155	15	1105
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	4	166	1105
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	149	21	1105
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	14	158	151	154	9	146	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105
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30																								31																							
36	42	44	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	159	11	1105	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	152	18	1105																				
145	45	62	67	79	84	92	104	109	123	25	4	166	1105	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	8	162	1105																				
143	77	82	96	99	116	121	52	57	65	27	8	162	1105	143	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	27	1	169	1105																				
141	106	111	119	50	55	69	72	89	94	29	6	164	1105	141	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	29	6	164	1105																				
139	71	49	54	93	74	88	118	105	113	31	5	165	1105	139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	5	165	1105																				
35	91	78	86	125	103	108	66	47	61	135	147	23	1105	35	117	103	75	83	85	87	95	67	53	135	147	23	1105																				
37	120	101	115	64	51	59	98	76	81	133	152	18	1105	37	115	101	90	88	81	86	80	69	55	133	159	11	1105																				
39	58	63	53	83	97	75	114	122	100	131	157	13	1105	39	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	131	157	13	1105																				
41	87	95	73	112	117	107	56	70	48	129	155	15	1105	41	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	129	155	15	1105																				
43	110	124	102	60	68	46	85	90	80	127	1	169	1105	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	4	166	1105																				
136	128	126	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	149	21	1105	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	149	21	1105																				
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156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105																				
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There are total 31 magic squares of order 13. Out of them first four are **centered** magic squares. First magic squares is **pandiagonal**. Magic squares 5, 6, 7 and 8 are **double digits bordered** magic squares. Magic squares numbers 9 to 31 are **cornered** magic squares. These **cornered** magic squares include as traditional as well as double digits magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11. Double digits magic squares are also embedded with cornered magic squares of lower orders. Complete list can be downloaded as **pdf file** from the link [2].

2.8 Magic Squares of Order 15

Below are few examples of different types of magic squares of order 15. These are **centered**, **bordered** and **cornered** magic squares.

	pan	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
1695	1	87	111	178	188	3	86	110	179	187	2	85	109	180	189	1695
1695	171	193	8	76	117	170	194	7	78	116	169	195	9	77	115	1695
1695	83	106	177	186	13	82	108	176	185	14	84	107	175	184	15	1695
1695	192	6	88	113	166	191	5	89	112	168	190	4	90	114	167	1695
1695	118	173	181	12	81	119	172	183	11	80	120	174	182	10	79	1695
1695	31	72	96	163	203	33	71	95	164	202	32	70	94	165	204	1695
1695	156	208	38	61	102	155	209	37	63	101	154	210	39	62	100	1695
1695	68	91	162	201	43	67	93	161	200	44	69	92	160	199	45	1695
1695	207	36	73	98	151	206	35	74	97	153	205	34	75	99	152	1695
1695	103	158	196	42	66	104	157	198	41	65	105	159	197	40	64	1695
1695	16	57	126	148	218	18	56	125	149	217	17	55	124	150	219	1695
1695	141	223	23	46	132	140	224	22	48	131	139	225	24	47	130	1695
1695	53	121	147	216	28	52	123	146	215	29	54	122	145	214	30	1695
1695	222	21	58	128	136	221	20	59	127	138	220	19	60	129	137	1695
1695	133	143	211	27	51	134	142	213	26	50	135	144	212	25	49	1695
1	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

	pan	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
1695	186	65	88	187	74	78	188	75	76	189	64	86	190	62	87	1695
1695	80	193	66	89	183	67	90	181	68	79	191	69	77	192	70	1695
1695	73	81	185	63	82	194	61	83	195	71	84	184	72	85	182	1695
1695	36	200	103	37	209	93	38	210	91	39	199	101	40	197	102	1695
1695	95	43	201	104	33	202	105	31	203	94	41	204	92	42	205	1695
1695	208	96	35	198	97	44	196	98	45	206	99	34	207	100	32	1695
1695	6	215	118	7	224	108	8	225	106	9	214	116	10	212	117	1695
1695	110	13	216	119	3	217	120	1	218	109	11	219	107	12	220	1695
1695	223	111	5	213	112	14	211	113	15	221	114	4	222	115	2	1695
1695	156	50	133	157	59	123	158	60	121	159	49	131	160	47	132	1695
1695	125	163	51	134	153	52	135	151	53	124	161	54	122	162	55	1695
1695	58	126	155	48	127	164	46	128	165	56	129	154	57	130	152	1695
1695	171	20	148	172	29	138	173	30	136	174	19	146	175	17	147	1695
1695	140	178	21	149	168	22	150	166	23	139	176	24	137	177	25	1695
1695	28	141	170	18	142	179	16	143	180	26	144	169	27	145	167	1695
2	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

3 mgc	1680	1710	1695	1680	1710	1695	1680	1710	1695	1680	1710	1695	1680	1710	1695
4	9	2	58	63	56	112	117	110	166	171	164	220	225	218	1695
3	5	7	57	59	61	111	113	115	165	167	169	219	221	223	1695
8	1	6	62	55	60	116	109	114	170	163	168	224	217	222	1695
157	162	155	211	216	209	40	45	38	49	54	47	103	108	101	1695
156	158	160	210	212	214	39	41	43	48	50	52	102	104	106	1695
161	154	159	215	208	213	44	37	42	53	46	51	107	100	105	1695
85	90	83	94	99	92	148	153	146	202	207	200	31	36	29	1695
84	86	88	93	95	97	147	149	151	201	203	205	30	32	34	1695
89	82	87	98	91	96	152	145	150	206	199	204	35	28	33	1695
193	198	191	22	27	20	76	81	74	130	135	128	139	144	137	1695
192	194	196	21	23	25	75	77	79	129	131	133	138	140	142	1695
197	190	195	26	19	24	80	73	78	134	127	132	143	136	141	1695
121	126	119	175	180	173	184	189	182	13	18	11	67	72	65	1695
120	122	124	174	176	178	183	185	187	12	14	16	66	68	70	1695
125	118	123	179	172	177	188	181	186	17	10	15	71	64	69	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

4 mgc	1638	1605	1416	1371	1320	1488	1680	1716	1896	2070	2013	1980	1791	1746	1695
97	100	80	82	81	222	225	205	207	206	47	50	30	32	31	1695
77	87	92	85	99	202	212	217	210	224	27	37	42	35	49	1695
78	86	88	90	98	203	211	213	215	223	28	36	38	40	48	1695
93	91	84	89	83	218	216	209	214	208	43	41	34	39	33	1695
95	76	96	94	79	220	201	221	219	204	45	26	46	44	29	1695
72	75	55	57	56	122	125	105	107	106	172	175	155	157	156	1695
52	62	67	60	74	102	112	117	110	124	152	162	167	160	174	1695
53	61	63	65	73	103	111	113	115	123	153	161	163	165	173	1695
68	66	59	64	58	118	116	109	114	108	168	166	159	164	158	1695
70	51	71	69	54	120	101	121	119	104	170	151	171	169	154	1695
197	200	180	182	181	22	25	5	7	6	147	150	130	132	131	1695
177	187	192	185	199	2	12	17	10	24	127	137	142	135	149	1695
178	186	188	190	198	3	11	13	15	23	128	136	138	140	148	1695
193	191	184	189	183	18	16	9	14	8	143	141	134	139	133	1695
195	176	196	194	179	20	1	21	19	4	145	126	146	144	129	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

5	mgc	1828	1720	1768	1602	1636	1676	1662	1736	1718	1750	1784	1622	1670	1558	1695
210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14	1695	
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224	1695	
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222	1695	
6	32	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	194	220	1695	
8	34	171	73	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	153	55	192	218	1695	
10	36	169	75	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	151	57	190	216	1695	
12	38	167	77	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	149	59	188	214	1695	
13	39	63	145	131	103	111	113	115	123	95	81	163	187	213	1695	
208	182	65	143	129	118	116	109	114	108	97	83	161	44	18	1695	
206	180	67	141	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	85	159	46	20	1695	
204	178	69	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	87	157	48	22	1695	
202	176	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	50	24	1695	
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26	1695	
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28	1695	
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

6	mgc	1870	1574	1581	1584	1945	1529	2190	1162	1593	1682	1750	2245	1194	1831	1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695	
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695	
201	25	62	85	168	66	80	162	159	163	72	69	157	220	6	1695	
216	10	164	141	58	160	146	64	67	63	154	153	73	45	181	1695	
11	215	152	74	121	98	108	101	137	120	106	144	82	48	178	1695	
41	185	169	57	105	128	118	125	89	93	133	70	156	23	203	1695	
193	33	79	147	102	124	116	109	114	90	136	170	56	175	51	1695	
197	29	59	167	127	99	111	113	115	130	96	150	76	208	18	1695	
17	209	68	158	95	131	112	117	110	132	94	53	173	222	4	1695	
3	223	143	83	107	119	91	122	129	100	123	60	166	1	225	1695	
8	218	87	139	134	92	135	104	97	126	103	148	78	211	15	1695	
195	31	172	54	171	77	86	75	155	81	65	165	142	28	198	1695	
19	207	88	138	55	149	140	151	71	145	161	61	84	210	16	1695	
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695	
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

7	mgc	1934	1507	1559	1656	1901	1524	2190	1162	1561	1704	1764	2203	1208	1857	1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695	
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695	
201	25	62	85	168	66	80	162	159	163	72	69	157	220	6	1695	
216	10	164	141	58	160	146	64	67	63	154	153	73	45	181	1695	
11	215	152	74	89	97	105	113	121	129	137	144	82	48	178	1695	
41	185	169	57	128	136	95	96	104	112	120	70	156	23	203	1695	
193	33	79	147	111	119	127	135	94	102	103	170	56	175	51	1695	
197	29	59	167	101	109	110	118	126	134	93	150	76	208	18	1695	
17	209	68	158	133	92	100	108	116	117	125	53	173	222	4	1695	
3	223	143	83	123	124	132	91	99	107	115	60	166	1	225	1695	
8	218	87	139	106	114	122	130	131	90	98	148	78	211	15	1695	
195	31	172	54	171	77	86	75	155	81	65	165	142	28	198	1695	
19	207	88	138	55	149	140	151	71	145	161	61	84	210	16	1695	
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695	
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

8	mgc	1918	1517	1590	1628	1931	1522	2190	1162	1602	1694	1753	2226	1178	1819	1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695	
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695	
201	25	62	85	168	66	80	162	159	163	72	69	157	220	6	1695	
216	10	164	141	58	160	146	64	67	63	154	153	73	45	181	1695	
11	215	152	74	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	144	82	48	178	1695	
41	185	169	57	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	70	156	23	203	1695	
193	33	79	147	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	170	56	175	51	1695	
197	29	59	167	131	118	111	113	115	108	95	150	76	208	18	1695	
17	209	68	158	129	103	116	109	114	123	97	53	173	222	4	1695	
3	223	143	83	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	60	166	1	225	1695	
8	218	87	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	148	78	211	15	1695	
195	31	172	54	171	77	86	75	155	81	65	165	142	28	198	1695	
19	207	88	138	55	149	140	151	71	145	161	61	84	210	16	1695	
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695	
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

9	mgc	1896	1674	1415	1711	1954	1595	2056	1158	1576	1612	1733	2124	1418	1808	1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695	
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695	
201	25	53	73	82	91	100	109	129	138	147	156	165	220	6	1695	
216	10	153	173	61	70	79	88	97	117	126	135	144	45	181	1695	
11	215	132	141	161	170	58	67	76	96	105	114	123	48	178	1695	
41	185	111	120	140	149	158	167	55	64	84	93	102	23	203	1695	
193	33	90	99	108	128	137	146	155	164	63	72	81	175	51	1695	
197	29	69	78	87	107	116	125	134	143	152	172	60	208	18	1695	
17	209	169	57	66	75	95	104	113	122	131	151	160	222	4	1695	
3	223	148	157	166	54	74	83	92	101	110	119	139	1	225	1695	
8	218	127	136	145	154	163	62	71	80	89	98	118	211	15	1695	
195	31	106	115	124	133	142	162	171	59	68	77	86	28	198	1695	
19	207	85	94	103	112	121	130	150	159	168	56	65	210	16	1695	
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695	
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

19	mgc	1755	1642	1548	2073	1513	1488	1965	1749	1298	1762	1499	2159	1695	1584	1695
110	117	112	125	101	127	99	144	82	67	159	52	174	9	217	1695	
115	113	111	124	102	133	93	142	84	64	162	41	185	3	223	1695	
114	109	116	104	122	94	132	79	147	167	59	40	186	8	218	1695	
108	106	123	107	121	89	137	78	148	168	58	184	42	205	21	1695	
118	120	103	105	119	92	134	140	86	63	163	50	176	7	219	1695	
90	91	131	128	129	126	96	138	88	62	164	191	35	201	25	1695	
136	135	95	98	97	130	100	146	80	171	55	195	31	213	13	1695	
149	153	87	83	81	151	85	76	152	172	54	190	36	206	20	1695	
77	73	139	143	145	75	141	74	150	71	155	45	181	1	225	1695	
70	60	69	170	165	72	169	66	68	173	161	51	175	203	23	1695	
156	166	157	56	61	154	57	160	158	65	53	196	30	6	220	1695	
180	34	182	183	179	32	187	33	177	38	178	37	29	215	11	1695	
46	192	44	43	47	194	39	193	49	188	48	197	189	10	216	1695	
224	221	211	26	17	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	27	210	28	1695	
2	5	15	200	209	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	199	198	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

20	mgc	1746	1635	1556	2077	1513	1503	1973	1741	1287	1762	1499	2159	1695	1584	1695
101	107	113	119	125	127	99	144	82	67	159	52	174	9	217	1695	
118	124	105	106	112	133	93	142	84	64	162	41	185	3	223	1695	
110	111	117	123	104	94	132	79	147	167	59	40	186	8	218	1695	
122	103	109	115	116	89	137	78	148	168	58	184	42	205	21	1695	
114	120	121	102	108	92	134	140	86	63	163	50	176	7	219	1695	
90	91	131	128	129	126	96	138	88	62	164	191	35	201	25	1695	
136	135	95	98	97	130	100	146	80	171	55	195	31	213	13	1695	
149	153	87	83	81	151	85	76	152	172	54	190	36	206	20	1695	
77	73	139	143	145	75	141	74	150	71	155	45	181	1	225	1695	
70	60	69	170	165	72	169	66	68	173	161	51	175	203	23	1695	
156	166	157	56	61	154	57	160	158	65	53	196	30	6	220	1695	
180	34	182	183	179	32	187	33	177	38	178	37	29	215	11	1695	
46	192	44	43	47	194	39	193	49	188	48	197	189	10	216	1695	
224	221	211	26	17	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	27	210	28	1695	
2	5	15	200	209	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	199	198	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

21	mgc	1767	1617	1564	2058	1513	1508	1956	1765	1283	1762	1499	2159	1695	1584	1695
122	105	125	107	106	127	99	144	82	67	159	52	174	9	217	1695	
102	112	117	110	124	133	93	142	84	64	162	41	185	3	223	1695	
118	111	113	115	108	94	132	79	147	167	59	40	186	8	218	1695	
103	116	109	114	123	89	137	78	148	168	58	184	42	205	21	1695	
120	121	101	119	104	92	134	140	86	63	163	50	176	7	219	1695	
90	91	131	128	129	126	96	138	88	62	164	191	35	201	25	1695	
136	135	95	98	97	130	100	146	80	171	55	195	31	213	13	1695	
149	153	87	83	81	151	85	76	152	172	54	190	36	206	20	1695	
77	73	139	143	145	75	141	74	150	71	155	45	181	1	225	1695	
70	60	69	170	165	72	169	66	68	173	161	51	175	203	23	1695	
156	166	157	56	61	154	57	160	158	65	53	196	30	6	220	1695	
180	34	182	183	179	32	187	33	177	38	178	37	29	215	11	1695	
46	192	44	43	47	194	39	193	49	188	48	197	189	10	216	1695	
224	221	211	26	17	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	27	210	28	1695	
2	5	15	200	209	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	199	198	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

32	mgc	1847	1561	1865	1622	1629	1941	1401	1724	1500	1817	2144	1546	1695	1438	1695
49	54	192	160	40	188	31	37	162	171	159	47	179	10	216	1695	
177	172	34	66	186	38	195	189	64	55	67	164	62	201	25	1695	
72	154	143	147	97	75	82	149	98	136	90	170	56	8	218	1695	
181	45	83	79	129	151	144	77	128	132	94	155	71	205	21	1695	
194	32	73	153	110	117	112	125	101	81	145	167	59	7	219	1695	
174	52	85	141	115	113	111	124	102	74	152	57	169	3	223	1695	
41	185	140	86	114	109	116	104	122	127	99	61	165	213	13	1695	
30	196	137	89	108	106	123	107	121	93	133	33	193	206	20	1695	
53	173	84	142	118	120	103	105	119	148	78	46	180	1	225	1695	
44	182	134	92	95	91	126	87	96	150	146	175	51	203	23	1695	
197	29	138	88	131	135	100	139	130	76	80	168	58	6	220	1695	
187	39	190	42	157	183	191	63	48	68	176	65	60	9	217	1695	
70	156	36	184	69	43	35	163	178	158	50	161	166	215	11	1695	
27	17	211	26	221	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	224	210	28	1695	
199	209	15	200	5	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	2	198	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

33	mgc	1792	1596	1865	1622	1629	1936	1406	1724	1494	1827	2142	1544	1695	1458	1695
49	54	192	160	40	188	31	37	162	171	159	47	179	10	216	1695	
177	172	34	66	186	38	195	189	64	55	67	164	62	201	25	1695	
72	154	143	147	97	75	82	149	98	136	90	175	51	8	218	1695	
181	45	83	79	129	151	144	77	128	132	94	155	71	205	21	1695	
194	32	73	153	104	120	115	112	114	81	145	167	59	7	219	1695	
174	52	85	141	122	106	111	125	101	74	152	57	169	3	223	1695	
41	185	140	86	116	110	113	102	124	127	99	61	165	213	13	1695	
30	196	137	89	118	108	109	123	107	93	133	33	193	206	20	1695	
53	173	84	142	105	121	117	103	119	148	78	46	180	1	225	1695	
44	182	134	92	126	95	91	87	96	150	146	170	56	203	23	1695	
197	29	138	88	100	131	135	139	130	76	80	168	58	6	220	1695	
187	39	190	42	157	183	191	63	48	68	176	65	60	9	217	1695	
70	156	36	184	69	43	35	163	178	158	50	161	166	215	11	1695	
27	17	211	26	221	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	224	210	28	1695	
199	209	15	200	5	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	2	198	16	1695	
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	

34 mgc	1822	1620	1826	1622	1627	1938	1406	1724	1512	1792	2160	1531	1695	1455	1695
49	54	192	160	40	188	31	37	162	171	159	47	179	10	216	1695
177	172	34	66	186	38	195	189	64	55	67	164	62	201	25	1695
72	154	143	147	97	75	82	149	98	136	90	175	51	8	218	1695
181	45	83	79	129	151	144	77	128	132	94	155	71	205	21	1695
194	32	73	153	122	105	125	107	106	81	145	167	59	7	219	1695
174	52	85	141	102	112	117	110	124	74	152	57	169	3	223	1695
41	185	140	86	118	111	113	115	108	127	99	61	165	213	13	1695
30	196	137	89	103	116	109	114	123	93	133	33	193	206	20	1695
53	173	84	142	120	121	101	119	104	148	78	46	180	1	225	1695
44	182	134	92	87	95	91	126	96	150	146	170	56	203	23	1695
197	29	138	88	139	131	135	100	130	76	80	168	58	6	220	1695
187	39	190	42	157	183	191	63	48	68	176	65	60	9	217	1695
70	156	36	184	69	43	35	163	178	158	50	161	166	215	11	1695
27	19	211	26	221	212	17	24	214	222	22	18	224	210	28	1695
199	207	15	200	5	14	209	202	12	4	204	208	2	198	16	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

There are total 41 magic squares of order 15. Out of them first five are **centered** magic squares. First two are **pandiagonal** magic squares. Magic squares numbers 6 to 13 are **double digits bordered** magic squares. Magic squares numbers 14 to 41 are **cornered** magic squares. These **cornered** magic squares include as traditional as well as double digits magic squares of orders, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13. Above we have written only few examples. Complete list as a **pdf file** can be download from the link [2].

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References

- [1] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <https://budshaw.ca/MagicSquares.html>
- [2] **Inder J. Taneja**, Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9212>.

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

• Bordered Magic Squares

- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.

- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>

• Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21 , 21^2 and 2021 . **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-118, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.

[22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>

[23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• **Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares**

[24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.

[25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Magic and Bordered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, September 10, pp. 1-99 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500134>.

[26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 8, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-80, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514396>.

[27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 10, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514398>.

[28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12, **Zenodo**, September 23, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5523608>.

[29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 14, **Zenodo**, September 26, pp. 1-198, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528867>.

[30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 3, **Zenodo**, May 05, pp. 1-29, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898383>.

[31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 5, **Zenodo**, May 06, pp. 1-31, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7903412>.

[32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 7, **Zenodo**, May 06, pp. 1-28, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7903420>.

• Magic Squares With Bordered Magic Rectangles

[33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319985>.

[34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 14 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319787>.

[35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-63, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320116>.

[36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320131>.

[37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320877>.

[38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 6 to 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225854>.

[39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Few Examples of Magic Squares of Even Orders 20 to 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, October 19, 2022, pp. 1-100, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225886>.

[40] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 24, 2023, pp. 1-76, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565946>

[41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40, **Zenodo**, January 30, 2023, pp. 1-102, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7585787>

- [42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 42 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-92, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695834>.
- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-69, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695939>
- [44] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696070>.
- [45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Closed Double-Cross Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 42, **Zenodo**, March 03, 2023, pp. 1-28, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7696181>.
- [46] **Inder J. Taneja**, 8000+ Magic Squares of Order 22 in Different Styles, Models and Designs, **Zenodo**, April 08, pp. 1-135, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809478>.

• Figured Magic Squares and Bordered Magic Rectangles

- [47] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 6, 10, 12, 14 and 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377674>.
- [48] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 18 and 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-87, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377689>.
- [49] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 22 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-61, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377706>.
- [50] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 24 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-104, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377779>.
- [51] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 26 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377794>.

- [52] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 28 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390666>.
- [53] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 30 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2022, pp. 1-179, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390705>.
- [54] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 32 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2022, pp. 1-310, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472891>.
- [55] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 34 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-193, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486540>.
- [56] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 36 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, December 27, 2022, pp. 1-140, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486548>.
- [57] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 38 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-133, <https://doi.org/110.5281/zenodo.7500188>.
- [58] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Order 40 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, January 03, 2023, pp. 1-157, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7500192>.

• Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares

- [59] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.
- [60] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.
- [61] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.

[62] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.

[63] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.

[64] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.

• Odd Order Magic Squares

[65] **Inder J. Taneja**, Odd Order Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 15, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043030>.

[66] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 17 and 19, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043105>.

[67] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 21 and 23, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-44, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043198>.

[68] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 25, **Zenodo**, June 15, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043228>.

• Cornered Magic Squares

[69] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.

[70] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.

[71] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39,
<https://10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.

• **Creative Magic Squares**

• **Creative Magic Squares**

[72] **Inder J. Taneja**, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations, **Zenodo**, June 22, pp. 1-45, 2021,
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009224>.
